

4G in the EU

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Territorial coverage of 4G in DESI countries averages 19%

The DESI Index calculates the value of the percentage of the national territory with 4G coverage. The data refer to the period 2016-2021. The DESI Index excludes the UK from the monitored countries.

Ranking of DESI countries by value of 4G coverage in 2021. Belgium, Denmark, Estonia, Malta, Sweden and Finland are in first place for value of 4G coverage with a value of 20.00. In the middle of the table are Spain with a value of 19.96 units, Portugal with a value of 19.95 units. Greece closes the ranking with a value of 19.73 units, Ireland with a value of 19.67 units and Slovakia with a value of 19.47 units. On average, the value of 4G coverage in the EU is equal to a value of 19.90 units.

Ranking of DESI countries by value of the percentage change in 4G coverage in the transition between 2016 and 2021. Bulgaria is in first place by value of the percentage change in the value of the DESI Index with an amount equal to a value of 641.11% at a value of 17.28 units, followed by Cyprus with a value equal to 194.91% equal to an amount of 13.13 units, and by Slovakia with a value equal to 175.45% equal to a value of 12, 4 units. In the middle of the table there are Austria with a value equal to 21.13% equal to an amount of 3.49 units, followed by Italy with a value of 19.41% equal to an amount of 3.21 units, and from Lithuania with a value of 19.36% equal to an amount of 3.24 units. Denmark closes the ranking with a value equal to 1.69% equal to an amount of 0.33 units, followed by Sweden with a value equal to 1.41% equal to an amount of 0.28 units and the Netherlands with a value equal to 1.41% equal to an amount of -0.04 units.

Variazione del valore percentuale della copertura territoriale del 4G tra il 2016 ed il 2021 nei paesi DESI							
Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per	Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per
1	Bulgaria	☆ 17,28	★ 641,1	15	Lithuania	★ 3,24	☆ 19,36
2	Cyprus	☆ 13,13	☆ 194,9	16	Ireland	★ 2,98	☆ 17,85
3	Slovakia	☆ 12,4	☆ 175,5	17	Finland	★ 2,62	☆ 15,1
4	Romania	☆ 11,18	☆ 128,5	18	Czechia	★ 2,01	☆ 11,2
5	Croatia	☆ 10,19	☆ 105,8	19	Germany	★ 1,9	☆ 10,58
6	Malta	☆ 9,33	☆ 87,5	20	Portugal	★ 1,86	☆ 10,3
7	France	☆ 7,42	☆ 59,25	21	Hungary	★ 1,43	☆ 7,77
8	Spain	☆ 6,93	☆ 53,19	22	Poland	★ 1,43	☆ 7,73
9	Greece	☆ 6,5	☆ 49,09	23	Slovenia	★ 1,42	☆ 7,68
10	Estonia	☆ 5,22	☆ 35,3	24	Luxembourg	★ 1,19	☆ 6,37
11	Belgium	☆ 4,8	☆ 31,57	25	Denmark	★ 0,33	★ 1,69
12	Latvia	★ 3,64	☆ 22,3	26	Sweden	★ 0,28	★ 1,41
13	Austria	★ 3,49	☆ 21,13	27	Netherlands	★ -0,04	★ -0,19
14	Italy	★ 3,21	☆ 19,41				

Figure 1. Change in the percentage value of 4G territorial coverage between 2016 and 2021 in DESI countries.

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Network analysis with Manhattan distance. A network analysis using the Manhattan distance is presented below. A single complex network structure is detected with the following connections, namely:

- Belgium has a connection with Finland for a value of 0.35 units;
- Finland has a connection with Belgium for a value of 0.35 units, with Denmark with a value of 0.37 units, with Sweden for a value of 0.38 units, and with the Poland for a value equal to a value of 0.25 units;
- Denmark has a connection with Finland for a value of 0.37 units, with Sweden with a value of 0.0091 units and with Poland for a value of 0.26 units;
- Sweden has a connection with Finland for a value of 0.38 units, with Denmark for a value of 0.0091 units and with Poland for an amount of 0.26 units ;
- Poland has a connection with Denmark for a value of 0.26 units, with Finland for an amount equal to 0.25 units, with Sweden for an amount of 0.26 units, and with the Czech Republic for a value of 0.39 units;
- The Czech Republic has a connection with Poland for a value of 0.39 units, with Lithuania for an amount of 0.34 units and with Portugal for an amount of 0.27 units;
- Lithuania has a connection with the Czech Republic for a value of 0.34;
- Portugal has a connection with the Czech Republic for a value of 0.27 units, with Slovenia for a value of 0.35 units, and with Luxembourg for a value of 0.38 units;
- Slovenia has a connection with Portugal for a value of 0.35 units;
- Luxembourg has a connection with Portugal worth 0.38 units.

Therefore, it appears that Poland is the most connected country in the dynamics of the evolution of 4G diffusion in the European Union.

Figure 2. Complex network structure detected through the use of network analysis optimized with the Manhattan distance method. As is evident, Poland is the most connected country in the dynamics of 4G diffusion in Europe

Conclusions. About 20% of the territory of the DESI countries is covered by the 4G network. However, this is a small value. Furthermore, it is very likely that there is a significant territorial

inequality between centers and peripheries in determining the level of 4G distribution. However, if we look at the gaps between the various countries, we see that they are very small. In fact, the countries that have the highest coverage value of 4G have a value of 20% while the last country has a coverage value of 19.47%. The diffusion of 4G is therefore not such as to guarantee total coverage of the territory of the DESI countries. The percentage of the territory covered by 4G is marginal in the context of DESI countries. The result is a difficulty in making the benefits of the fourth industrial revolution available to a large part of the European population. However, given that 4G is also closely connected to the application of the Internet of Things-IoT, it is difficult to introduce forms of smart manufacturing in the absence of a significant enhancement of the new types of internet connection.

Countries	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Austria	★ 16,50	★ 19,66	★ 19,67	★ 19,82	★ 19,85	★ 19,99
Belgium	★ 15,20	★ 19,98	★ 20,00	★ 20,00	★ 20,00	★ 20,00
Bulgaria	★ 2,70	★ 12,18	★ 17,30	★ 19,58	★ 19,83	★ 19,98
Croatia	★ 9,63	★ 16,70	★ 18,27	★ 19,19	★ 19,78	★ 19,82
Cyprus	★ 6,74	★ 11,42	★ 16,00	★ 19,07	★ 19,87	★ 19,87
Czechia	★ 17,92	★ 19,80	★ 19,80	★ 19,80	★ 19,95	★ 19,93
Denmark	★ 19,67	★ 20,00	★ 20,00	★ 20,00	★ 20,00	★ 20,00
Estonia	★ 14,78	★ 19,59	★ 19,48	★ 19,75	★ 19,81	★ 20,00
Finland	★ 17,37	★ 20,00	★ 19,88	★ 19,99	★ 20,00	★ 20,00
France	★ 12,51	★ 17,94	★ 19,33	★ 19,78	★ 19,85	★ 19,93
Germany	★ 18,00	★ 18,87	★ 18,83	★ 19,17	★ 19,54	★ 19,90
Greece	★ 13,23	★ 16,71	★ 17,99	★ 19,39	★ 19,71	★ 19,73
Hungary	★ 18,34	★ 19,53	★ 19,73	★ 19,73	★ 19,74	★ 19,77
Ireland	★ 16,69	★ 18,92	★ 19,05	★ 18,61	★ 19,67	★ 19,67
Italy	★ 16,56	★ 19,41	★ 19,56	★ 19,62	★ 19,63	★ 19,77
Latvia	★ 16,34	★ 17,66	★ 19,48	★ 19,53	★ 19,98	★ 19,98
Lithuania	★ 16,75	★ 19,63	★ 19,69	★ 19,73	★ 19,99	★ 19,99
Luxembourg	★ 18,74	★ 19,37	★ 19,53	★ 19,56	★ 19,93	★ 19,93
Malta	★ 10,67	★ 19,83	★ 19,97	★ 19,97	★ 20,00	★ 20,00
Netherlands	★ 19,87	★ 19,78	★ 19,78	★ 19,78	★ 19,80	★ 19,83
Poland	★ 18,53	★ 19,97	★ 19,97	★ 19,98	★ 19,97	★ 19,97
Portugal	★ 18,09	★ 19,60	★ 19,63	★ 19,74	★ 19,91	★ 19,95
Romania	★ 8,71	★ 11,73	★ 17,86	★ 18,76	★ 19,70	★ 19,89
Slovakia	★ 7,07	★ 16,77	★ 18,76	★ 19,12	★ 19,84	★ 19,47
Slovenia	★ 18,55	★ 19,13	★ 19,52	★ 19,90	★ 19,90	★ 19,98
Spain	★ 13,03	★ 18,14	★ 19,07	★ 19,84	★ 19,92	★ 19,96
Sweden	★ 19,72	★ 20,00	★ 20,00	★ 20,00	★ 20,00	★ 20,00

Figure 3. Evolution of data relating to the application of 4G in DESI countries. As is evident, there has been a growth in the spread of 4G. However, no country exceeds 20% of the territorial coverage obtained through the use of 4G.

Declarations

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